

**STUDY OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF IONITES
OBTAINED ON THE BASE OF WALNUT SHELL AS A NATURAL
POLYMER**

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Annotation: *This research work was investigated based on the static exchange capacity (SAS) value of sulfocationite based on walnut shell cellulose. The modification of sulfuric acid to walnut shell was studied. In the following work, some physico-chemical properties of sulfocationite were obtained from cellulose of walnut husks, which are discarded as waste for the purpose of wastewater treatment. The structural morphology of the obtained samples before and after modification was studied on the basis of microphotographs taken using a scanning electron microscope.*

The water of Chirchik and Akhangaran rivers is also polluted. This includes the addition of waste from industrial, household and utility enterprises, treatment, sanitation and recreation areas, various mineral and organic fertilizers, and highly toxic chemical agents used in the fight against pests to the water. showing the effect of z. This causes the deterioration of the ecological situation and the increase of various diseases among the population. [1-2].

In this case, microphotographs of the natural polymer cellulose obtained from the original walnut shell, sodium metal absorbed cellulose, calcium metal absorbed cellulose and polymers containing sulfo groups are presented in the following pictures. When we look at the surface of the cellulose in the walnut shell, we can see pores with an average size of 6.5 nm (Fig. 2(a)).

It can be seen from the micrographic structure of the sample containing sulfo group attached to cellulose (Fig. 2- (b)) that all areas of this sorbent surface consist of pores with almost the same structure. Such a structure improves the adsorption of metal ions on the surface of the sorbent. Figure 2 (c and d) shows that the polymer morphological structure has changed as a result of the sorption of sulfocationite metal ions. possible [3-4]

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of (a) cellulose, (b) SO₃H sulfocationite, (c) sodium metal doped sulfocationite, and (d) calcium metal doped cellulose sulfocationite polymers.

The sulfocationite based on the cellulose extracted from the walnut shell has the property of sorption of metal ions from various solutions, and the SAS according to NaOH was found to be equal to 3.36 mgeq/g.

Take one gram of the resulting sample and put it in 100 ml solution of sodium alkali (NaOH) 0.1 N for one day and wash it again in distilled water until pH value becomes neutral. The sample is then treated with a 0.1 N solution of hydrochloric acid to activate it. Cationite in a neutral state is left for one day in a solution of 0.1 N sodium hydroxide. The following formula was used to calculate the SAS value of cationite:

$$CAC_{\text{kaunium}} = \frac{100 \cdot k_1 - \frac{100}{10} \cdot k_2 \cdot a}{10 \cdot g}$$

$k_1 = V(\text{acid})/V(\text{alkali}) = 1$ theoretical, $k_2 = V(\text{initial alkali})/V(\text{acid})$, a – volume of acid spent on sorbed NaOH, g – mass of sorbent, SAS mg·eq/g.

$$k_1 = \frac{V_1}{V_2} = 1 \quad k_2 = \frac{10}{5.95} = 1.68$$

$$CAC = \frac{100 \times 1 - \frac{100}{10} \times 1.68 \times 3.95}{10 \times 1} = 3.36$$

IR (infrared) - spectrum analysis

An IR (infrared)-spectrum analysis was performed to identify the resulting sulfocationite. IR-spectrum analysis of walnut shell cellulose, sample after attachment of Na metal to cellulose, sample after attachment of sulfo group (sulfocationite) and samples after Sa metal was carried out. In the IR-spectrum of glucose, an absorption region indicating valence vibrations of the –OH and group at a wavelength of 3100 cm⁻¹ was observed, as well as SN2 at 2900 cm⁻¹ vibrations of groups are formed and -ON, -SH- groups in the region of 1423-1321 cm⁻¹, -S-O-S- valence vibrations of ether bonds are observed in the range of 1000-1150 cm⁻¹.

Figure 1. (a) cellulose, (b) sodium cellulose (calcified cellulose and (d) IR spectra of sulfocationite